


```

type: numeric daily date (float)

range: [21685,22250] units: 1
or equivalently: [16may2019,01dec2020] units: days
unique values: 360 missing .: 22,304/29,124

mean: 22012.6 = 07apr2020 (+ 15 hours)
std. dev: 182.242

percentiles:      10%      25%      50%      75%      90%
                 21767    21831    22078    22177    22225
                 06aug2019 09oct2019 12jun2020 19sep2020 06nov2020

```

gender_adult

Parent gender

```

type: numeric (byte)
label: genderlabel

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 0/29,124

tabulation: Freq.  Numeric  Label
             17,634      0  Female
             11,490      1  Male

```

gender_child

Child gender

```

type: numeric (byte)
label: genderlab

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 0/29,124

tabulation: Freq.  Numeric  Label
             14,161      0  Girls
             14,963      1  Boys

```

ethnicity_child

Ethnicity: Danish, Other Western, Non-Western

```

type: numeric (float)
label: ethniclevel

```

range: [1,3] units: 1
 unique values: 3 missing .: 0/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	25,427	1	Danish background
	743	2	Other Western background
	2,954	3	Non-Western background

sendout_date **Date survey was sent**

type: numeric daily date (**float**)

range: [21685,22218] units: 1
 or equivalently: [16may2019,30oct2020] units: **days**
 unique values: 9 missing .: 0/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Value
	2,146	21685 16may2019
	2,892	21756 26jul2019
	2,887	21805 13sep2019
	3,301	21875 22nov2019
	3,302	21959 14feb2020
	1,425	22078 12jun2020
	1,751	22092 26jun2020
	5,737	22162 04sep2020
	5,683	22218 30oct2020

age_child **Age - years at survey invitation**

type: numeric (**float**)

range: [6.0095825,11.660506] units: 1.000e-07
 unique values: 2,048 missing .: 0/29,124

mean: 8.79275
 std. dev: 1.44561

percentiles:	10%	25%	50%	75%	90%
	6.76523	7.57016	8.84052	10.037	10.7324

age_adult **Age - years at survey invitation**

type: numeric (**float**)
 range: [22.220396,76.804932] units: 1.000e-06
 unique values: 8,649 missing .: 0/29,124

 mean: 40.428
 std. dev: 5.86277

 percentiles: 10% 25% 50% 75% 90%
 32.9446 36.3915 40.3491 44.3012 47.7125

age_child_cat Age - years at survey invitation (categorical)

type: numeric (**float**)
 label: **agechildcatlabel**

 range: [1,5] units: 1
 unique values: 5 missing .: 0/29,124

 tabulation:

Freq.	Numeric	Label
4,112	1	6 years
5,557	2	7 years
5,866	3	8 years
6,077	4	9 years
7,512	5	10-11 years

municipal Municipality

type: numeric (**float**)
 label: **municipallabel**

 range: [1,10] units: 1
 unique values: 10 missing .: 0/29,124

 examples:

1	Odense
4	Faaborg-Midtfyns
7	Nordfyns
9	Kolding

isced_adult ISCED: Parental educational level 0-3, 4-6, 7-8

type: numeric (**float**)
 label: **iscedlab**
 range: [1,3] units: 1
 unique values: 3 missing .: 23,564/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	1,986	1	Level 0-3
	2,454	2	Level 4-6
	1,120	3	Level 7-8
	23,564	.	

singleparent

One adult in the household

type: numeric (**float**)
 label: **singleparentlabel**
 range: [0,1] units: 1
 unique values: 2 missing .: 23,545/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	4,540	0	No
	1,039	1	Yes
	23,545	.	

siblingyesno

Siblings in the households

type: numeric (**float**)
 label: **siblab**
 range: [0,1] units: 1
 unique values: 2 missing .: 23,850/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	4,649	0	Yes
	625	1	No
	23,850	.	

own_laptop

Item 5: Laptop

type: numeric (**byte**)
 label: **pil_sp10_1_**

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 22,707/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	4,820	0	Nej
	1,597	1	Ja
	22,707	.	

own_stationaryPC

Item 5: StationaryPC

type: numeric (byte)
label: pil_sp10_2_

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 22,747/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	5,916	0	Nej
	461	1	Ja
	22,747	.	

own_tablet

Item 5: Tablet

type: numeric (byte)
label: pil_sp10_3_

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 22,642/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	2,529	0	Nej
	3,953	1	Ja
	22,642	.	

own_smartphone

Item 5: Smartphone

type: numeric (byte)
label: pil_sp10_4_

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 22,672/29,124


```
percentiles:      10%      25%      50%      75%      90%
                  0        1        2        3        4
```

```
movies_tv_td           Item 9: Weekday - Movies, TV shows, YouTube etc.
```

```
type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp15_hvdg_1_, but 8 nonmissing values are not lab
> eled
```

```
range: [0,330]           units: .1
unique values: 9         missing .: 22,715/29,124
```

```
tabulation: Freq.   Numeric  Label
              511     0      Ingen
              513     7.5
              1,222   22.5
              2,264   45
              1,324   90
              383    150
              120    210
              55     270
              17     330
              22,715 .
```

```
games_td           Item 9: Weekday - Games (on smartphone, tablet, game console, PC)
```

```
type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp15_hvdg_2_, but 8 nonmissing values are not lab
> eled
```

```
range: [0,330]           units: .1
unique values: 9         missing .: 22,717/29,124
```

```
tabulation: Freq.   Numeric  Label
              964     0      Ingen
              1,009   7.5
              1,220   22.5
              1,525   45
              1,152   90
              376    150
              101    210
              45     270
              15     330
              22,717 .
```

socialmedia_comm_td**Item 9: Weekday - Social media or other types of communication**

type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp15_hvdg_5_, but 8 nonmissing values are not lab
> eled

range: [0,330] units: .1
unique values: 9 missing .: 22,729/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	4,617	0	Ingen
	1,178	7.5	
	359	22.5	
	139	45	
	63	90	
	19	150	
	5	210	
	7	270	
	8	330	
	22,729	.	

othertypes_td**Item 9: Weekday - Other (for example, drawing programs etc.)**

type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp15_hvdg_99_, but 8 nonmissing values are not la
> beled

range: [0,330] units: .1
unique values: 9 missing .: 22,725/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	5,040	0	Ingen
	676	7.5	
	396	22.5	
	152	45	
	65	90	
	17	150	
	7	210	
	7	270	
	39	330	
	22,725	.	

socialmedia_comm_wend**Item 9: Weekend day - Social media or other types of communication**

type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp16_wend_5_, but 8 nonmissing values are not lab
> eled

range: [0,330] units: .1
unique values: 9 missing .: 22,796/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	4,640	0	Ingen
	954	7.5	
	385	22.5	
	190	45	
	93	90	
	30	150	
	15	210	
	9	270	
	12	330	
	22,796	.	

othertypes_wend**Item 9: Weekend day - Other (for example, drawing programs etc.)**

type: numeric (float)
label: pil_sp16_wend_99_, but 8 nonmissing values are not la
> beled

range: [0,330] units: .1
unique values: 9 missing .: 22,797/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	5,171	0	Ingen
	453	7.5	
	306	22.5	
	216	45	
	93	90	
	25	150	
	7	210	
	9	270	
	47	330	
	22,797	.	

screen_td_cat Item 9: Categorical total screen media use for a typical weekday

type: numeric (**float**)
label: **cat_screenlab**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,726/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	1,611	1	0-1 hrs
	1,970	2	>1-2 hrs
	1,219	3	>2-3 hrs
	703	4	>3-4 hrs
	895	5	>4 hrs
	22,726	.	

screen_wend_cat

Item 9: Categorical total screen media use for a typical weekend day

type: numeric (**float**)
label: **cat_screenlab**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,797/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	843	1	0-1 hrs
	1,346	2	>1-2 hrs
	1,352	3	>2-3 hrs
	992	4	>3-4 hrs
	1,794	5	>4 hrs
	22,797	.	

screen_td_4hours

Item 9: >4 hours of total screen media use for a typical weekday

type: numeric (**float**)

range: [0,1] units: 1
unique values: 2 missing .: 22,726/29,124

```

tabulation:  Freq.  Value
              5,503  0
              895   1
              22,726 .

```

screen_wend_4hours

Item 9: >4 hours of total screen media use for a typical weekend day

```

type: numeric (float)

range: [0,1]                units: 1
unique values: 2            missing .: 22,797/29,124

```

```

tabulation:  Freq.  Value
              4,533  0
              1,794  1
              22,797 .

```

screen_30minawake_alltd

Item 12: Screen media within 30 minutes after awakening on all weekdays

```

type: numeric (float)
label: scr30week

range: [0,1]                units: 1
unique values: 2            missing .: 22,934/29,124

```

```

tabulation:  Freq.  Numeric  Label
              4,527    0      0-4 weekdays
              1,663    1      All weekdays
              22,934    .

```

screen_30minawake_allwend

Item 12: Screen media within 30 minutes after awakening on all weekend days

```

type: numeric (float)
label: scr30weekend

range: [0,1]                units: 1
unique values: 2            missing .: 22,969/29,124

```


tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	2,290	1	Strongly agree
	1,194	2	Agree
	703	3	Neither agree or disagree
	1,166	4	Disagree
	919	5	Strongly disagree
	22,852	.	

rules_howmuch

Item 11: There are fixed boundaries for how much time the child may use screen
> m

type: numeric (**byte**)
label: **agreelabel**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,887/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	1,682	1	Strongly agree
	2,065	2	Agree
	907	3	Neither agree or disagree
	1,106	4	Disagree
	477	5	Strongly disagree
	22,887	.	

rules_when

Item 11: There are fixed boundaries for when the child may use screen media du
> ri

type: numeric (**byte**)
label: **agreelabel**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,887/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	2,036	1	Strongly agree
	2,201	2	Agree
	756	3	Neither agree or disagree
	870	4	Disagree
	374	5	Strongly disagree
	22,887	.	

rules_what_play

Item 11: There are fixed boundaries for what games the child is allowed to play

type: numeric (**byte**)
label: **agreelabel**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,891/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	2,492	1	Strongly agree
	2,127	2	Agree
	717	3	Neither agree or disagree
	627	4	Disagree
	270	5	Strongly disagree
	22,891	.	.

rules_what_watch

Item 11: There are fixed boundaries for what movies etc. the child may watch

type: numeric (**byte**)
label: **agreelabel**

range: [1,5] units: 1
unique values: 5 missing .: 22,892/29,124

tabulation:	Freq.	Numeric	Label
	2,283	1	Strongly agree
	2,299	2	Agree
	765	3	Neither agree or disagree
	637	4	Disagree
	248	5	Strongly disagree
	22,892	.	.

meanscreen_adult_hrs

Item 19: Weighted total screen media use for a typical day hrs

type: numeric (**float**)

range: [0,23.17857] units: 1.000e-08
unique values: 671 missing .: 23,470/29,124

weight_response

Inverse value of the predicted probability

type: numeric (**float**)

range: [3.0374808,16.831427] units: 1.000e-07
unique values: 29,083 missing .: 0/29,124

mean: 5.90704
std. dev: 1.70409

percentiles:	10%	25%	50%	75%	90%
	4.21572	4.65993	5.49821	6.76916	7.95691

2 . log close

name: <unnamed>

log: /Users/jespedersen/OneDrive - Syddansk Universitet/SCREENS_generere

> lt/Manuscript - SCREENS survey/5. draft/description of surveydata.smcl

log type: smcl

closed on: 12 Apr 2021, 13:38:16
